

Illegal Drug Related Social Media Data Detection and Classification Using Ensemble Learning

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Abstract

Illegal drugs use is a critical public health problem and it can lead to serious medical consequences like addiction, and even overdose deaths. Also, it is a big threat to law enforcements in worldwide communities. The most commonly used illegal drug is Cannabis, also called marijuana. Cocaine, MDMA/Ecstasy, GHB, Hallucinogens, Heroin, Inhalants, Ketamine, Methamphetamine are some of commonly use drugs in the world. Those drugs can categorize as Depressants, Stimulants and Hallucinogens. It is very hard to retrieve real-time information related to this domain. For real-time data retrieval, social media always used by researchers. People are sharing valuable information such as their thoughts, opinions, personal life details, their experiences, news and also their medical situations on social media. Because of this, researchers are increasingly turning in to social media as a potent data source. Researchers demonstrate social media has potential to uncover knowledge about many domains such as discrimination detection, influenza epidemic discovery, sentiment analysis and sexual health monitoring. This study demonstrate social media is also a potential real-time data source to discover illegal drugs related information. It shows social media is a good source to monitor illegal drug related incidents. With comparing commonly used machine learning algorithms and ensemble learning models to classify illegal drug related real-time data from social media, this study shows ensemble learning models shows better accuracy than other machine learning algorithms.

Keywords: *Classification, Ensemble learning, Filtering, Illegal drugs, Machine learning, Real time data, Social media*

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List of Abbreviations

ML	-	Machine Learning
SVM	-	Support Vector Machine
API	-	Application Programming Interface
CSV	-	Comma Separated Values
JSON	-	JavaScript Object Notation
IC	-	Inclusion Criterion
EC	-	Exclusion Criteria
URL	-	Uniform Resource Locator
IEEE	-	Institute of Electrical and Electronic Engineers
DBMS	-	Database Management System
AI	-	Artificial Intelligence

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Chapter 1

1. Introduction

1.1 Background

Illegal drug use has become a large public health problem and it is a devastating problem in communities. It can lead to serious medical consequences like addiction, and even overdose deaths. This is becoming a major problem in public health and threat to law enforcement worldwide with opioids causing the most harm and accounting for 76 percent of deaths where drug related, according to the latest World Drug Report, released by the United Nations Office on Drugs and Crime (UNODC). [1]

A drug is a substance that affects the way the body functions. If a drug is classified as 'illegal', this means that it is forbidden by law. Different illegal drugs have different effects on people and these effects are influenced by many factors. This makes them unpredictable and dangerous, especially for young people. The most commonly used illegal drug is Cannabis, also called marijuana. Cocaine, MDMA/Ecstasy, GHB, Hallucinogens, Heroin, Inhalants, Ketamine, Methamphetamine are some of commonly use drugs in the world. Those can classify as Depressants, Stimulants and Hallucinogens. "Depressants" are the drugs that slow down the central nervous system and the messages that go between the brain and the body. "Stimulants" are drugs that stimulate the central nervous system and speed up the messages going between the brain and the body. "Hallucinogens" are drugs which typically alter how a person perceives the world.

When considering drugs, people use different name in different places. Also, those illegal drugs have different commercial names and street names. As examples heroin called brown sugar, china white, white horse, skink, junk, H, smack, dope, horse etc. Marijuana called ganja, herb, Mary Jane, weed, sinsemilla, bud, blunt, dope, grass, joint etc. Likewise, every illegal drug has different names in different places in the word.

1.1.1 Importance of social media as a data source

People are discussing their thoughts, opinions, details of their life, their experiences and also their medical situations on public websites like social media sites. Facebook, Twitter and Instagram are some examples. This results in generating vast amount of data every second. For some researches, need to be done with real-time data. real-time data retrieval needs consciously updating information. Social media is such a data source.

Researchers are increasingly turning to social media as a potent information source. Because it has potential to uncover knowledge about many things including discrimination detection, influenza epidemic discovery, sentiment analysis, sexual health monitoring, and pharmacovigilance. Also, Social media is a potential data source for illegal drugs related data detection. It can lead to recognize patterns and draw conclusions. [2]

Figure 1 - Number of social media users worldwide from 2010 [3]

This figure 1 shows number of social media users in the world from 2010. It shows users increase in large numbers every year. In 2019 there are more than 2.77 billion social media users in the world. [3] So, those users generate huge amount of data related

to various fields and researcher can use those data to get information. This research investigates potentiality of those data to get illegal drugs related information.

1.1.2 Why twitter data is effective

Twitter is one of the most popular free social networking microblogging service that allows members to broadcast posts called tweets. Currently twitter has more than 115 million monthly active users and there are approximately 500 million tweets per day.

Because of it has huge number of active users, it generates huge amount of data. Also, those data are timely and it has ability to identify the best pattern related to various topics. So those data are very valuable for other companies, governments and also those data are importance to researchers all over the word.

Figure 2 - Leading countries based on number of Twitter users as of April 2019 [4]

This figure 2 shows top countries with the greatest number of twitter users. United State has more than 49.45 million users. In Japan there are more than 38.35 active twitter users. Also, millions of users in other countries all over the word too. [4]

Data generated from those users have potential to retrieve various kind of information because people post tweets about all kind of things like personal information, feelings, opinions, about other thing they know etc. Twitter save those data with lot of attributes

like user data, locations, data sources etc. Also, those are updated and real-time data. So, those data have a good value to lot of domains.

So, Twitter data also effective to retrieve information related to illegal drugs. This research uses Twitter streaming API and uses data retrieving model to get data. Also, tries to get data sets with low noises and gets balanced data sets. [5]

1.2 Motivation

Drugs related causes are one of top causes of death in the world. Drug usage has become a one of large public health problem in the world. Because of that lot of researchers trying to investigate this problem and implements a surveillance for illegal drug use and prescription medication abuse. To address this epidemic, need a real-time data to retrieve information. So, researchers of this research motivate to investigate a potential real-time data source.

Researchers are increasingly turning to social media as a potent information source. [6] Because it has potential to uncover knowledge about many things including discrimination detection, influenza epidemic discovery, sentiment analysis, sexual health monitoring, and pharmacovigilance. So, motivation is to use social media as a potential data source for illegal drug related data retrieval and classification for analyzing those data to reveal information about illegal drugs. So, this research will help to decrease world illegal drug problem.

1.3 Research Significance

With Social media, researchers can use real-time streaming data. It is a good source because, with those data researcher can retrieve timely information. Most social media platforms provide APIs for this retrieve real-time streaming data. [7] But those retrieval is often noisy and ambiguous because it streams non-related data too. So, this research use filtering model with key words for gather illegal drug related data with low noises. Because of that, this research uses very balanced data set for classification.

Ensemble methods are meta-algorithms that combine several machine learning techniques into one predictive model. So, this research investigates the use of ensemble learning model for classifying social media data and compare with other machine learning algorithms.

1.4 Research Objectives and Goals

This research focusing on using social media to retrieve illegal drugs related data. Currently, social media use to retrieve data for many kinds of causes. So, it is very potential data source for researchers. Primary goal this research is to demonstrate the possibility of utilizing social media for retrieve illegal drugs related data.

Researcher use many kinds of machine learning algorithms to classify social media data. SVM, Naïve Bayes, Decision Tree and Random Forest are some of those commonly used machine learning algorithms. Compare those algorithms for classify social media data is another goal of this research. It helps to find the most suitable machine learning algorithms for social media data sets. Also, this research use ensemble learning models for classification and compare with other models.

1.5 Problem Statement and Research Questions

Problem is, how to use twitter social media to retrieve illegal drugs related data and classify those data as related and non-related classes. This study has set out the specific focus of the investigating utilizing social media for retrieving illegal drugs related data and classify using machine learning models like ensemble learning to address and summarize the following Research Questions (RQs).

RQ1: Is there a possibility of utilizing social media for retrieving illegal drugs related data by users all over the world?

Many researchers use social media as potential data source for various kind of researches like sentiment analysis in various domains, sexual health monitoring of users etc. In this research, researchers see about potentiality of social medias like twitter to retrieve illegal drugs related information.

RQ2: How to collect illegal drugs related data from social media with low noises to get more accurate result?

When research's use social media as a data source, it contains lots of unrelated data. So, this research tries to find a way to retrieve data related to illegal drugs from twitter social media with low noises and see how it will affect the final results.

RQ3: Use machine learning algorithms to classify illegal drugs related data and non-related data from the data sets and check the accuracy of those machine learning algorithms.

Lot of related researches commonly use machine learning algorithms like SVM, Naïve Bayes, Decision Tree, Random Forest. Those algorithms give different results for their data sets. This research compares some results from those algorithms.

RQ4: Demonstrate ensemble learning methods are more suitable or not than those commonly used machine learning algorithms for illegal drugs related data classification?

This research uses ensemble learning method to classify retrieving data to illegal drugs related and non-related classes. Also compares with other machine learning models to choose suitable machine learning model.

This research focus on retrieving illegal drugs related data from twitter and use ensemble learning methods and other machine learning algorithms for classifying those data and investigate those results to draw conclusions.

1.6 Novelty of the Research

When use data sources like twitter, it contains various kind of data related to different domains and those data have various kind of attributes. So, most of things are not related to the domain and need to remove those noises. This research use keyword filtering based data collecting method to gather streaming data related to illegal drugs from twitter. Because of that, data set is more balanced and it contains low noises. Also, this research uses a selected drug related keyword set contains categories, drug names, commercial and street names, behavior related keywords etc. for filtering. With this method, this research collects very balanced tweets data set with low noises.

Related researches for this research use machine learning algorithms like SVM, Naïve Bayes, Decision Tree and Random Forest for classify tweets. This research use ensemble method for classification. Ensemble methods are meta-algorithms that combine several machine learning techniques into one predictive model in order to decrease variance(bagging), bias (boosting), or improve predictions (stacking). This research demonstrates and investigates use of ensemble learning models to classify tweets as illegal drug related and non-related classes.

1.7 Thesis Organization

1.7.1 Chapter 01 – Introduction

This chapter contains the background of the research, motivation for this research, research significance, research objective and goals, problem statement, research questions which focusing and novelty of the research.

In background, researchers introduce what are the illegal drugs and discuss about how illegal drugs affect the communities. Also, why social media is a potential source for detect illegal drug related data and why researcher use Twitter as social media data source.

In motivation, researchers declared what are the factors that motivate researchers to investigate about illegal drugs and conducted this research on use social media to detect illegal drug related data and us machine learning to classify those data.

In research significance, researchers discussed about why is this research about illegal drugs related data detection from social media is important and what kind of impact it will be to the communities.

In research objective and goals, researchers describe what are goals intent to achieve from this research and objective of the researchers.

In problem statement and research questions, researchers declare what is the problem this research going to be address. It is the problem statement of this study. Also, researchers discussed what are the research questions which this study going to be answered.

In novelty of the research, researchers explain what are new methods this research propose and why this research different from other related researches.

1.7.2 Chapter 02 - Literature Review

Researchers investigates previous researches related to this research domain. This part includes that, how this mapping study conducted and about the importance of this mapping study. Also, it consists with summaries of primary studies related to the topic and sub-topics derived from that topic. That summaries describes methodologies use in those studies, gaps in those studies, and results from those studies.

1.7.3 Chapter 03 - Research Method

This chapter includes the methodology use to conduct this research. It explains data collection methods used in this study, what are the preprocessing methods that used, how those data stored and what are the machine learning algorithms used to classify those data. Also, this chapter gives introductions to techniques and technologies used in this research and explain about machine learning algorithms used in the study.

1.7.4 Chapter 04 – Design Implementation and Analysis of the Result

This chapter describes how researchers conducted this study and what are the design and implementations researchers did in this study. Also, this chapter includes about the technologies that used in the study. It also shows results of this study which got by analyzing data and results from different machine learning algorithms.

1.7.5 Chapter 05 – Discussion, Conclusion and Recommendations

This chapter discusses about results from the different machine learning algorithms and compares those results. Researcher discusses about potential of social media as a data source to detect illegal drug related data and which information can retrieve from those data. Also, this chapter includes how ensemble learning algorithms give results compares to other algorithms.

Chapter 2

2. Literature Review

2.1 Introduction

Intentions of conducting mapping studies are to generally provide a broad overview of a specific topic and also investigating the need of more primary studies related and sub-topics derived from that topic. In this case, the investigation done on social media illegal drug data classification. It focuses on identifying and classifying all the previous research related to a social media data mining and machine learning based on topic 'Illegal drug related data classification'. This mapping study includes previously published studies since 2000 to 2019. Other studies on data mining and machine learning in social media also taken into the account of this study.

2.2 Mapping methodology

In this research, the mapping study methodology is following the guidelines and process proposed by Kitchenham and Charters. It contains three major phases such as planning, conducting and reporting.

Planning phase contains pre-review activities, inclusion and exclusion criteria, sources of studies, search string and mapping procedures. According to Kitchenham and Charters guidelines, in conducting phase, related studies are searched and selected from previously collected data. Selected search strings and snowballing method use in conducting phase. Finally, in the reporting phase, researches compared results and investigated those results to get a better understanding of the research domain.

2.3 Sources

For this mapping study six electronic databases were identified and used which contains studies more appropriate to the research domain of this study. After that searching criteria was performed in these six electronic databases.

- i. IEEE Xplore (<http://ieeexplore.ieee.org>)
- ii. Springer Link (<https://link.springer.com>)
- iii. Science Direct (<https://www.sciencedirect.com>)
- iv. Emerald Insight (<http://emeraldinsight.com>)

- v. Research Gate (<https://www.researchgate.net>)
- vi. ACM Digital Library (<https://dl.acm.org>)

2.4 Terms and search strings

Conduct this mapping study researchers of this study used the search string and applied those in metadata fields such as title, abstract, URL and keywords. For this search researchers use few electronic databases such as IEEE Xplore, ACM Digital Library, Springer Link, Science direct, Research gate and Emerald Insight.

Table 1 – Search terms of the tertiary study on Illegal drug related data detection

Areas	Search terms
Illegal Drugs related data detection	<i>“Illegal drugs related data detection”, “Drugs related real-time data detection”</i>
Review	<i>“systematic literature review”, “systematic review”, “systematic mapping”, “mapping study”, “systematic literature mapping”</i>
Search string	<i>(“Illegal drug related data detection OR Drugs related real-time data detection”) AND (“systematic literature review” OR “systematic review” OR “systematic mapping” OR “mapping study” OR “systematic literature mapping”)</i>

Table 2 – Search terms of the tertiary study on Social media data detection

Areas	Search terms
Social media data retrieving	<i>“Social media data retrieving”, “Real-time data detection about illegal drugs in social media”</i>
Review	<i>“systematic literature review”, “systematic review”, “systematic mapping”, “mapping study”, “systematic literature mapping”</i>
Search string	<i>(“Social media data retrieving OR Real-time data detection about illegal drugs in social media”) AND (“systematic literature review” OR “systematic review” OR “systematic</i>

	<i>mapping” OR “mapping study” OR “systematic literature mapping”)</i>
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Table 3 – Search terms of the tertiary study on Social media illegal drugs related data classification

Areas	Search terms
Social media data classification	<i>“Social media data classification”, “Social media illegal drugs related data classification”</i>
Review	<i>“systematic literature review”, “systematic review”, “systematic mapping”, “mapping study”, “systematic literature mapping”</i>
Search string	<i>(“Social media data classification OR Social media illegal drugs related data classification”) AND (“systematic literature review” OR “systematic review” OR “systematic mapping” OR “mapping study” OR “systematic literature mapping”)</i>

2.5 Inclusion and exclusion criteria

To select better researches from those studies, researcher used one inclusion criterion (IC) and five exclusion criteria (EC). Using those criteria this mapping study selected some studies related to the research domain.

Table 4 - Inclusion criterion in selection process

No.	Inclusion criterion (IC)
IC1	The paper discusses knowledge sharing in software companies

Table 5 - Exclusion criteria in selection process

No.	Exclusion criteria (EC)
EC1	The paper does not contain an abstract
EC2	The paper is published just as an abstract
EC3	The language used in writing the paper is not English
EC4	The paper is a previous version of a study already selected
EC5	The paper is not a primary study. It is either an editorial or a summary

2.6 Data extraction and synthesis

Figure 3 - Search and selection process

This study used total of 35 studies from different electronic databases. Researchers choose 10 studies from IEEE Xplore, 5 studies from Springer Link, 6 studies in

Science Direct, 3 studies from Emerald, 5 studies from ACM and 6 studies from Research Gate.

Those selected 35 studied process by the search and selection process shows in the figure 3. In the stage 1, duplications were removed from the selected pool. In the stages 1 to 5, one inclusion criterion (IC), five exclusion criteria (EC) and snowballing method were applied to the studies pool. From this searching and selection process finally 6 studies were chosen to investigate related to the research domain. Table 6 shows those studies selected from the process.

Table 6 - Selected studies from mapping study

ID	Bibliographic reference
#1	T. Ding, A. Roy, Z. Chen, Q. Zhu and S. Pan, "Analyzing and Retrieving Illicit Drug-Related Posts from Social Media," in 2016 IEEE International Conference on Bioinformatics and Biomedicine (BIBM), 2016.
#2	H. Hu, P. Moturu, K. N. Dharan, J. Geller, S. D. Iorio and H. Phan, "Deep Learning Model for Classifying Drug Abuse Risk Behavior in Tweets," in 2018 IEEE International Conference on Healthcare Informatics, 2018
#3	N. Phan, S. A. Chun, M. Bhole and J. Geller, "Enabling Real-Time Drug Abuse Detection in Tweets," in 2017 IEEE 33rd International Conference on Data Engineering, 2017.
#4	A. Roy, A. Paul, H. Pirsiavash and S. Pan, "Automated Detection of Substance Use-Related Social Media Posts Based on Image and Text Analysis," in 2017 International Conference on Tools with Artificial Intelligence, 2017.
#5	B. S. Raja, A. Ali, M. Ahmed and A. Khan, "Semantics Enabled Role Based Sentiment Analysis for Drug Abuse on Social Media: A Framework".
#6	Y. Zhou, N. Sani, C.-K. Lee and J. Luo, "Understanding Illicit Drug Use Behaviors by Mining Social Media," 2016.

Selected researches show in table 6, were studies for the primary study to understand research gaps of each selected researches, different methodologies, results and recommendations.

2.7 Related Works

Social media stream data in real-time and it is a good source of timely information, which is potent and critical for monitoring emerging drug use trends. To facilitate information retrieval, most social media platforms provide APIs. This retrieval contains lot of unrelated data to each domain. Related works to this study used those data retrieving methods.

Study based on Analyzing and Retrieving Illicit Drug-Related Posts from Social Media from Tao Ding, Arpita Roy, Zhiyuan Chen, Qian Zhu and Shimei published 2016 IEEE International Conference on Bioinformatics and Biomedicine, [8] researcher use hashtags to detect related data and used 371 hashtags to collect data from Instagram social media users.

Rank	Method 1			Method 2	Method 3
	#marijuana	#fentanyl	#percocet	#fentanyl	#percocet
1	#cannabiscommunity	#hospital	#oxycodone	#oxycotin	#oxycodone
2	#cannabis	#midazolam	#xans	#lateralthinking	#hydros
3	#weed	#anesthesia	#roxicodone	#addrell	#oxys
4	#medicalmarijuana	#surgery	#oxys	#lortabs	#roxicodone
5	#herb	#medicine	#roxicodone	#hydrocodone	#kpins
6	#420	#ouch	#vicodin	#somas	#roxies
7	#maryjane	#wisdomtooth	#hydros	#nocros	#percocets
8	#pot	#katemine	#hydrocone	#alprazolam	#perces
9	#highlife	#painmeds	#percs	#vicodin	#oxycontin
10	#kush	#fentanylpatch	#roxy30s	#xanaxbars	#xans
11	#stonned	#demerol	#oxycontin	#ritalin	#hydrocodone
12	#cannabisconcentrates	#ativan	#dilaudid	#klonopin	#roxy30s
13	#weedporn	#painrelief	#opiates	#methadone	#roxicodone
14	#cannabisculture	#tramadol	#kpins	#xans	#rocicet
15	#trichomes	#sedation	#xanax	#Lol	#roxys
16	#weedstagram	#painpatch	#percocets	#benzos	#dilaudid
17	#ganja	#er	#roxies	#ativan	#vicodin
18	#drug	#trauma	#nacrotic	#qualitest	#xanax
19	#weedsociety	#icu	#roxycet	#actavis	#klonopin
20	#hash	#tocillectomy	#roxy	#pillpopper	#opiates

Figure 4 - keywords used in the study [8]

Figure 4 shows example hashtag methods use in the study. According to the study, with newly collected hashtags, that model can retrieve more detection from Instagram. But

social media users of Instagram mainly focus on posting photos. So, text classification on Instagram data is not so much effective.

Preliminary evaluation using a small ground truth dataset for k-means clustering algorithm and it indicated that the system is able to retrieve drug related posts with 78.1% accuracy. But researchers in that described dataset is too small and need a large data set.

In Han Hu, Pranavi Moturu, Kannan Neten Dharan, James Geller, Sophie Di Iorio and Hai Phan's study about Deep Learning Model for Classifying Drug Abuse Risk Behavior in Tweets, it described three key components of a drug abuse tweet surveillance system. A large-scale data collection and annotation component, our boosting deep learning model that detects drug abuse tweets, and the geospatial and semantic analytics component are those components. [9] In that study researchers collect data using drug names as filters and carried out a semantic analysis. The semantic analysis of this study identified positive drug abuse behavior related data can use for uncovers many drug terms to be used for ontology refinement, and geospatial analysis of that research allows hotspot identification of drug related behavior locations such as geo distribution of drug abuse positive tweets in the United States shows in the figure 5.

Figure 5 - hotspot identification from geospatial analysis [9]

Strategy of that study produced dataset with 3102 positive and 3677 negative tweets in total and it is tested with traditional and state-of-the-art machine learning approaches

and Monte Carlo cross validation. Model of that study achieved 86.53% accuracy, 88.6% recall and 86.63% F1-score.

Study of Nhathai Phan, Manasi Bhole, Soon Ae Chun and James Geller about Enabling Real-Time Drug Abuse Detection in Tweets study, researchers demonstrate that illicit drug abuse and prescription drug abuse can be detected in twitter data using unified framework. [2]

In this study, Drug Abuse Detection System has four steps. Tweet collection through streaming API, Data management by using DBMS (Data Base Management System), Reprocessed and filtered tweets are first three steps. After that result data fed into data analysis with artificial intelligent (AI) systems to identify drug abuse related tweets. Trained system from this study, used in different drug abuse monitoring services. Also, this study compares results from different machine learning algorithms.

Models	Precision	Recall	F-Measure
Random Forest	0.718	0.710	0.649
Decision Tree (J48)	0.748	0.757	0.746
SVM	0.733	0.741	0.734
Naïve Bayes	0.694	0.653	0.662

Figure 6 - Different machine leaning models [2]

This figure 6 shows the recall, precision and F-measure of different commonly use machine learning algorithms used for this model. Decision tree J48 showed the highest results of 0.748 Precision, 0.757 Recall and 0.746 F-Measure.

In the study about Automated Detection of Substance Use Related Social Media Posts Based on Image and Text Analysis by Arpita Roy, Anamika Paul, Hamed Pirsiavash and Shimei Pan used the state-of-the-art image and text analytics to identify and classify illicit drugs related social media posts. [10]

In this study, researchers collect social media data from Instagram. Instagram mostly contains Images. So, researchers extract both image features and text features. Study used neural network-based image and text feature extraction methods.

Figure 7- Architecture of the methodology [10]

Figure 7 shows architecture used in that study. Researchers used randomly chosen 80% of data for training data and rest 20% as the test data and use result of text classification model combined with image feature classification model to get accuracy, precision, recall and F1 measure. Figure 8 shows those results.

Model	Accuracy	Precision	Recall	F1 measure
Combined Model	90%	74%	77%	75%

Figure 8 - accuracy, precision, recall and F1 measure of combined model [10]

Based on literature of Semantics Enabled Role Based Sentiment Analysis for Drug Abuse on Social Media Framework study, from Bilal Saeed Raja, Ahmad Ali, Mansoor Ahmed and Abid Khan, they implemented a novel framework that facilitates web-based

research on the prohibited use of pharmaceutical drug abuse through the combination of various specialized domains of data mining and web semantic technologies. [11] Figure 9 shows the diagram of proposed framework for this study.

Figure 9 - Proposed framework of the study [11]

According to the study of Understanding Illicit Drug Use Behaviors by Mining Social Media research by Yiheng Zhou, Numair Sani, Chia-Kuei Lee and Jiebo Luo, they proposed an effective way to update sensitive-term dictionaries for illicit drugs. It is important because of the ever-changing keywords used to refer to drugs. [12] Study used Instagram as the social media data source and fetch data using hashtags. This research retrieves 58512 post as JSON data and convert them to CSV format and use

Apriori algorithm. A common challenge with flagging sensitive posts is the language. It is constantly changing and new words being added always to the drug vocabulary.

Figure 10 - Drug Popularity for Different Drugs from analysis [12]

Figure 10 shows the results from drug popularity analysis for different drugs. That study compared results from Instagram data with NSDUG 2014 data. Both of that showed similar kind of result.

Those information from selected related studies which selected by the mapping study are investigated by researchers to identifies research gaps, previously used methodologies and drawbacks in those methodologies. Those insights were helpful in conducting this study and researchers try to find solutions to those problems.

Chapter 3

3. Research Method

This research collects related data from social media and classify those as illegal drugs related and non-related data using machine learning techniques. Also compares different machine learning algorithms and investigate the results.

3.1 Data Source

For this research researchers use Twitter social media as the data source to collect relevant data because there are approximately 500 million tweets per day a day. That's lot of data contains various kind of information. Also, Twitter provide API called "Twitter Streaming API" interact with twitter data. [13] It can use for collecting real-time streaming data.

Application Programming Interface (API) is set of instructions created to interact with some technology. In this case Twitter provides open APIs to interact with their data. This research uses Twitter streaming API to interact with twitter data. Streaming API pushes data as tweets happen in near real-time. In order to access Twitter Streaming API, need Twitter developer account and four credentials from Twitter. Those are API key, API secret, Access token and Access token secret.

Twitter Streaming API pushes data in JSON objects. The Tweet object has list of 'root-level' attributes. It has fundamental attributes such as id, created_at, and text. This text attribute contains the status post by the user. Tweet objects are also the parent object to some child objects. Tweet child objects include user, entities, and extended_entities. Also Tweet object contains the geo location of the user who generating those data. Geo-tagged have a place child object.

```
{
  "created_at": "Wed Jun 10 20:19:24 +0000 2019",
  "id": 1050118621198921728,
  "id_str": "1050118621198921728",
  "text": "you don t realize how many people actually do cocaine till you get older",
  "user": {},
  "entities": {},
}
```

Figure 11 - Sample Tweet object with sample attributes [14]

Figure 11 shows the format of example Tweet object. The JSON will be a mix of ‘root-level’ attributes and child objects. It shows some fundamental attributes such as id, created_at, and text and child objects such as user. [14]

For this research mainly focus on text attribute. It is the attribute which contains data posted by the user. But in data retrieving process, this model saves all raw data pushes from twitter streaming API.

Twitter streaming API has some limitations. The default access level of Twitter streaming API allows up to use 400 track keywords, 5000 follow userids and also 25 0.1-360-degree location boxes. [15] Enterprise access of the Twitter streaming API gives parameters more than default level access.

3.2 Keyword filtering

Social media data have lot of unrelated data. In this case Twitter data mostly contains non-related data to illegal drugs. To keep balance between coverage and quality of data, this research uses illegal drugs related keywords as filters. That way can retrieve data with low noises.

In this research, researchers select some commonly used illegal drugs retrieve data according to few drug categories. Cannabinoids, Opioids, Stimulants, Club drugs, Dissociative drugs and Hallucinogens are those illegal drugs categories. In cannabinoids category there are drugs like marijuana and hashish. Opioids category has heroin and opium. In stimulants category, there are illegal drugs like cocaine, amphetamine and methamphetamine. Club drugs category for retrieve data related to illegal drugs like MDMA, flunitrazepam and GHB. In dissociative drugs category there are drugs like ketamine, PCP and analogs, salvia divinorum, DXM. Finally, in the hallucinogen category contains illegal drugs like LSD, mescaline and psilocybin.

For illegal drugs, people use different name in different places in the world. Also, those illegal drugs have different commercial names and street names. So, researchers consider those fact also to retrieve related data. As an example, marijuana called ganja, herb, Mary Jane, weed, sinsemilla, bud, blunt, dope, grass, joint etc. For LSD people called acid, blotter, cubes, microdot, yellow sunshine and blue heaven. Heroin called brown sugar, china white, white horse, skink, junk, H, smack, dope, horse etc. Likewise,

researcher created a key word list containing commercial names and street names for selected commonly used illegal drugs. Bellow mentions some key words use in this research with categories.

Table 7 - category, name, commercial & streets names of Stimulants

STIMULANTS	
Category & name	Example of commercial & street names
Cocaine	<i>Cocaine, blow, bump, candy, Charlie, coke, crack, flake, rock, snow, toot</i>
Amphetamine	<i>amphetamine, biphphetamine, Dexedrine, bennies, black beauties, crosses, hearts, LA turnaround, speed, truck drivers, uppers</i>
Methamphetamine	<i>methamphetamine, meth, ice, crank, chalk, crystal, fire, glass, go fast, speed</i>

Table 8 - category, name, commercial & streets names of Opioids

Opioids	
Category & name	Example of commercial & street names
Heroin	<i>heroin, smack, horse, brown sugar, dope, junk, skag, skunk, white horse, China white</i>
Opium	<i>opium, laudanum, paregoric, big O, black stuff, block, gum, hop</i>

Table 9 - category, name, commercial & streets names of Cannabinoids

Cannabinoids	
Category & name	Example of commercial & street names
Marijuana	<i>marijuana, blunt, ganja, grass, herb, joint, bud, maryJane, pot, reefer, green, trees, smoke, sinsemilla, skunk, weed, "cannabis",</i>
Hashish	<i>hashish, boom, gangster, hash, hashoil, hemp</i>

Table 10 - category, name, commercial & streets names of Dissociative drugs

Dissociative drugs	
Category & name	Example of commercial & street names
Ketamine	<i>ketamine, Ketalar SV, cat Valium, Special K, vitamin K</i>
PCP	<i>PCP, Phencyclidine, angel dust, boat, hog, love boat, peace pill</i>
Salvia Divinorum	<i>Salvia, Shepherdess Herb, Maria Pastora, magic mint, Sally D</i>
DXM	<i>DXM, dextromethorphan, Robotripping, Robo, Triple C</i>

Table 11 - category, name, commercial & streets names of Hallucinogens

Hallucinogens	
Category & name	Example of commercial & street names
LSD	<i>LSD, acid, blotter, cubes, microdot, yellow sunshine, blue heaven</i>
Mescaline	<i>mescaline, buttons, cactus, mesc, peyote</i>
Psilocybin	<i>psilocybin, Magic mushrooms, purple passion, shrooms, little smoke</i>

Table 12 - category, name, commercial & streets names of Club drugs

Club drugs	
Category & name	Example of commercial & street names
MDMA	<i>MDMA, Ecstasy, Adam, clarity, Eve, lovers speed, Molly, peace, uppers</i>
Flunitrazepam	<i>flunitrazepam, Rohypnol, forget me pill, Mexican Valium, R2, roach, Roche, roofies, roofinol, rope, rophies</i>
GHB	<i>GHB, Georgia home boy, grievous bodily harm, liquid ecstasy, soap, scoop, goop, liquid X</i>

3.3 Preprocessing data

Twitter streaming API pushes data in json objects. This research saves those raw data in json type files and extract needed data from those data afterwards. Researchers mainly focus on text attribute because it contains data posted by the users. Also, there are other important attributes like user, geo location, user verification details, followers count etc.

Collected raw data from Twitter streaming API and filtering method to json files need preprocessing. Those raw data often incomplete, inconsistent and likely to contain many errors. Data preprocessing is for resolving such issues. Data preprocessing prepares those raw data for further possessing.

When considering a tweet object some of attributes contains numeric data and some of them are nominal data. As examples text attribute contains nominal data and followers count is numeric. Those nominal data must clean because they have unwanted data like

punctuations, special strings, emojis etc. This Research, researcher clean those nominal data for further processing.

Preprocessed data are storing in a csv file. CSV (Comma-Separated Value) is a file format such as spreadsheet or database, used to store data. CSV files are easy to use access through tools such as WEKA. [16]

3.4 Classification

The goal of this data classification is to automatically classify unlabeled tweets. In this study, different supervised machine learning models are used for comparing. There are many different algorithms for text classification. Machine learning models like SVM (Support Vector Machine), Naïve Bayes, Random Forest, Decision Tree(J48) and Ensemble learning models are used for this task in this research.

3.4.1 Support Vector Machine, Naïve Bayes, Decision Tree(J48) and Random Forest

SVM is a machine learning algorithm that determines the best decision boundary between vectors that belong to a given category and vectors that not belong to it. So, In SVM text have to be transformed into vectors. Vectors means list of numbers which represent a set of coordinates in some space. When SVM determines the decision boundary, it decides where to draw the best line. That line divided space into two subsets. One for vectors which belong to category and other is foe vectors do not belong to that category.

Naïve Bayes also an algorithm which commonly applied for text classification. It is based on Bayes' theorem in probability and assumptions of this algorithm are very simple. It relies on a very simple representation of the document. It called the bag of word representation. It uses words related to each category and use those words to classify unlabeled data.

Decision tree algorithm is a supervised learning algorithm and it can used for solving regression and classification problems. It can use to create a training model which can use to predict class of a data by learning decision rules from prior data. This algorithm solves problems using tree representation. Each internal node represents an attribute

and each leaf node represent a class label. Decision tree J48 is the implementation of algorithm Iterative Dichotomiser 3(ID3).

Random forest is one of supervised machine learning algorithm based on ensemble learning. It combines multiple algorithm of the same type multiple decision trees. This random forest algorithm also can be used for solve both regression and classification problems. In this each tree is trained on a subset of data. So, the random forest algorithm relies on the power of the crowd. Because of that random forest algorithm is not biased.

3.4.2 Ensemble learning classification

Ensemble learning methods are meta-algorithm type machine learning algorithms that combine several machine learning algorithms into one predictive model. This combine done because in order to decrease variance(bagging), bias(boosting) or improve predictions(stackng). So, ensemble learning helps to improve machine learning result. Some ensemble learning methods use same type learners and some ensemble learning methods use different types of learners.

There are two groups of ensemble methods such as sequential ensemble methods and parallel ensemble methods. In sequential ensemble methods, base learners are generated sequentially. Adaboost algorithm is one example for sequential ensemble method. In parallel ensemble methods, base learners are generated in parallel. As an example, Random Forest is parallel ensemble method.

3.4.2.1 Bagging

Bagging use homogeneous weak learners and learns them independently in parallel and combines them in deterministic averaging process.

3.4.2.2 Boosting

Boosting also often use homogeneous learners and learn them sequentially. Its base model depends on the previous one. After combine them following one of deterministic strategy.

3.4.2.3 Stacking

Stacking considers heterogeneous learners and learn them parallelly. Then combines them by training a meta-model. Its output prediction based on predictions of different models. [17]

Chapter 4

4. Design Implementation and Analysis of the Result

4.1 Data Collecting

Data collecting in this study done by using Twitter streaming API. So, firstly Twitter developer account is created. [18] Twitter requires some details such as purpose of using the API, Commercial use of this API etc. for create a Twitter developer account. Sometime it takes one or two days to get access.

Twitter streaming API need four credentials from Twitter developer account. So, access token was created to get API key, API secret, Access token and Access token secret. Twitter streaming API pushes near real-time tweet objects in JSON format. So, python program was created to catch and save those JSON objects. Tweepy library was use for this program. Tweepy library supports interact with Twitter data via basic authentication using Twitter Access Token. [19]

Data collecting program was develop with keyword filtering method. Researchers selected some commonly used illegal drugs and data collecting program was developed to retrieve data using that keyword list. That keyword lists were created using drug names, category names, commercial and street names of those drugs and also with keywords related to behaviors. So, real-time streaming Twitter data which related to selected drugs were collected under Cannabinoids, Opioids, Stimulants, Club drugs, Dissociative drugs and Hallucinogens categories in JSON files.

4.2 Preprocess Data

For preprocess those stored data another python program was created. This program used for clean and retrieve needed features from those stored data. Data previously stored from Twitter streaming API contains lot of unwanted data. So, researchers extracted needed information such as Text, User information, Geo location, Verification details etc. unwanted data like punctuations, special strings, emojis etc. were removed by cleaning. Those preprocessed data were saved in CSV file by the program. That CSV file was created with different columns for each attribute.

4.3 Analyzing the Dataset

Figure 12 - Count of tweets variance related to filers

Figure 12 shows collected data count related to filter categories used in this study. Keyword lists were used for those Stimulants, Opioids, Hallucinogens, Dissociative drugs, Club drugs and Cannabinoids categories. Most of data found in Twitter data set related to Cannabinoids, Opioids and Stimulants. Data which related to Opioids, Hallucinogens, Dissociative drugs and Club drugs are lesser than that.

For those data, Sentiment analysis were performed. Researchers developed another python program for that. Using that program data set categorized in Neutral, Positive and Negative classes. Figure 13 shows variance of those data counts.

Figure 13 - Negative, Neutral, Positive Tweet count variance

Researchers used Text attribute for that. If user's data contained positive idea, it categorized as Positive. If the idea was negative, it categorized as Negative. Otherwise, it categorized as Neutral. Figure 15 shows count of each data.

When analyzing user's verification details in those data set, most of tweets posted by non-verified users. Figure 14 shows there are only few of users which in the data set were verified users.

Figure 14 - User verification variance

4.4 Data Classification

Researchers randomly selected 500 tweet dataset and investigated those data. They manually categorized those data to classes. Data which related to illegal drug categorized under related class and data which not related to illegal drugs categorized under non-related class. Researchers created separate data sheet using those data and it was used to train machine learning algorithms.

In this study researchers selected Support Vector Machine algorithm, Naïve Bayes algorithm, Decision Tree algorithm, Random Forest algorithm and some Ensemble learning models. Bellow results were got by those algorithms.

Table 13 - Results from SVM algorithm

Class	Related	Non-related	Weighted Avg
Precision	0.845	0.692	0.806
Recall	0.926	0.496	0.817
F-Measure	0.883	0.578	0.806

Table 14 - Results of Naive Bayes algorithm

Class	Related	Non-related	Weighted Avg
Precision	0.792	0.660	0.759
Recall	0.955	0.260	0.779
F-Measure	0.866	0.373	0.742

Table 15 – Result of Decision Tree algorithm

Class	Related	Non-related	Weighted Avg
Precision	0.792	0.906	0.821
Recall	0.992	0.228	0.799
F-Measure	0.881	0.365	0.750

Table 16 - Result of Random Forest algorithm

Class	Related	Non-related	Weighted Avg
Precision	0.801	0.971	0.844
Recall	0.997	0.268	0.813
F-Measure	0.889	0.420	0.770

Random Forest algorithm categorized as an Ensemble approach machine learning algorithm. Also, researcher investigated results from other Ensemble learning models too. This study used Bagging, Boosting and stacking machine learning models.

Class	Related	Non-related	Weighted Avg
Precision	0.808	0.974	0.850
Recall	0.997	0.299	0.821
F-Measure	0.893	0.783	0.482

Table 17 - Result of meta.Bagging algorithm

Class	Related	Non-related	Weighted Avg
Precision	0.786	0.962	0.879
Recall	0.997	0.197	0.327
F-Measure	0.889	0.795	0.740

Table 18 - Result of AdaBoostM1 algorithm

Chapter 5

5. Discussion, Conclusion and Recommendation

This study investigated the potential of social media data for illegal drug related information detection. For the selected drugs in Stimulants, Opioids, Hallucinogens, Dissociative drugs, Club drugs and Cannabinoids categories data retrieving method detected real-time data successfully. In this case, researchers use Twitter as the social media data source. Result set proves this data source has potential to reveal information related to illegal drugs.

Rather than retrieve every data object streaming real-time in social media, use specific filtering method to track data is more successful because it consists low noises. So, researchers were able to get accurate results with those data. With this data collecting method researcher can collect real-time data from social media for any research domain.

Traditional data collecting methods consist lot of unrelated data. Because of that machine learning algorithms can't use those data for training. This filtering method also can use in other domains such as discrimination detection, influenza epidemic discovery, sentiment analysis, sexual health monitoring, and pharmacovigilance etc.

Researchers investigated results from those selected algorithms such as Support Vector Machine algorithm, Naïve Bayes algorithm, Decision Tree algorithm and Random Forest algorithm. Also, same data set were used with Ensemble learning models. For this, researchers used Bagging ensemble approach, Boosting ensemble approach and Stacking ensemble approach. For each of those algorithms, precision, Recall, F-measure were investigated. Also, researchers compared results from those algorithms with each algorithm.

For the data set, confusion matrix of each algorithm was retrieved and by researchers. With those confusion matrixes researcher investigated correctly classified instances in both Related and Non-Related classes. Also, accuracy of each classifier is calculated for comparison.

Table 19 - Result from different algorithms

Algorithm	SVM	Naïve Bayes	Decision Tree	Random Forest	Bagging	AdaBoost
Precision	0.806	0.759	0.821	0.844	0.850	0.879
Recall	0.817	0.779	0.799	0.813	0.821	0.327
F-Measure	0.806	0.742	0.750	0.770	0.482	0.740

Investigating those results and confusion matrixes from each machine learning algorithm for given data set, Ensemble learning models showed better accuracy than Support vector machine algorithm, Naïve Bayes algorithm and Decision tree algorithm. Bagging and AdaBoost approaches shows the highest precision. So, Ensemble learning is a better approach from those selected machine learning algorithms for data sets such as social media data.

From the investigation and comparing different ensemble learning approaches, this study shows Bagging approach shows better accuracy than other approaches. So, it shows bagging approach is better approach to use for these kind of data sets.

This study recommends to use social media data for retrieve illegal drug related information. Because social media has potential to discover such information. Social media can use in real-time monitoring for illegal drugs related activities. That information can use to reduce health problems related to illegal drugs. Also, that information can use by law enforcements all over the world to reduce drug related incidences.

Machine learning models used to classify social media data in every domain. This study shows Ensemble learning models are a better approach to classify social media data such as Twitter data. It showed a better accuracy than other commonly used machine learning algorithms.

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